

Impact of Solvent Polarity on the Photoinduced Dynamics of a Push-Pull Molecular Motor

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Abstract: Light-driven rotary molecular motors convert light energy into unidirectional rotational movement. In overcrowded alkene-based molecular motors, rotary motion is accomplished through consecutive cis-trans photoisomerization reactions and thermal helix inversion steps. To date, a complete understanding of the photoisomerization reactions of overcrowded alkene motors has not been achieved yet. In this work, we use quantum chemical calculations and quantum mechanics/molecular mechanics (QM/MM) nonadiabatic dynamics simulations to investigate the photoinduced dynamics of a push-pull alkene-based molecular motor in two different solvents: cyclohexane and methanol. We show that, while in both solvents the main photorelaxation pathway of our investigated push-pull motor involves two different excited-state minima, in polar methanol the photorelaxation dynamics is much faster than in nonpolar cyclohexane because of two main effects: (i) a lowering of the energy barrier between the excited-state minima, and (ii) a reduction of the energy gap with the ground state at the largely twisted dark minimum, where the excited-state decay takes place. Both effects can be attributed to solvent-polarity

stabilization of the charge-transfer excited state along the photorelaxation pathway. In line with the experimental findings, our simulations also indicate that in methanol the accelerated photoinduced dynamics goes along with a faster fluorescence decay and a large reduction in the forward photoisomerization yield of our investigated motor.

1 Introduction

Artificial molecular motors are synthetic molecules engineered to convert the supplied energy into controlled motion at the molecular level¹⁻⁵. This capability makes them key components for the design of molecular machines, which are nanometer-sized devices performing specific functions in a controlled manner⁶⁻⁸.

Among the most promising artificial molecular motors are light-driven rotary molecular motors, which convert light energy into unidirectional rotational motion. The earliest light-driven rotary motors were developed by the Nobel laureate Feringa and coworkers, and are generally called chiral overcrowded alkenes^{2,9-11}. A typical Feringa's motor is made of two chemical moieties connected by a double bond and combines two chiral elements, namely helicity and one or two stereocenters (Figure 1a). The unidirectional 360° rotation of one moiety with respect to other is achieved through consecutive photochemical and thermal steps (Figure 1b): two energetically uphill light-driven reactions, called cis-trans photoisomerizations (steps 1 and 3), and two energetically downhill thermal helix inversions (steps 2 and 4).

Figure 1: **a** Molecular structure of the push-pull overcrowded alkene-based first-generation motor **1** investigated in this work, along with the definition of the most important geometrical coordinates of **1** and a side view of the quantum mechanics/molecular mechanics (QM/MM) system employed in the nonadiabatic dynamics simulations. **b** Photocycle of unidirectional rotation for motor **1**, comprising two cis-trans photoisomerizations of the central double bond (steps 1 and 3), and two thermal helix inversions (steps 2 and 4).

The efficiency of light-driven rotary motors depends on both the rates of thermal helix inversions, which are the rate-determining steps for rotation, and the quantum yields of photoisomerization reactions^{12,13}. The first-generation class of Feringa's alkene motors, which include two stereogenic centers (one on each half of the motor, Figure 1a), is characterized by high quantum yields of forward photoisomerization (up to 99%)^{14–16}, but is limited by relatively low rates of thermal helix inversions. To overcome this limitation, Feringa and coworkers developed a second class of overcrowded alkene motors, named second-generation molecular motors, comprising an extended aromatic group (e.g. fluorene) and only one stereogenic center. Second-generation motors exhibit higher rates of rotations¹⁷, compared to first-generation motors, demonstrating successful control of the thermal helix inversion rate by synthetic variation. However, second-generation motors typically feature low yields of forward photoisomerization, not exceeding 20–30%^{18,19}, a limitation which calls for novel strategies to design more efficient rotary motors.

At the current stage of research, a controlled manipulation of the photoisomerization efficiency of light-driven rotary motors has not yet been attained. Achieving such a control requires a detailed characterization of the photoisomerization reactions of light-driven rotary motors, which are not yet fully understood.

The photochemical behaviour of Feringa's alkene motors has been extensively investigated by time-resolved spectroscopy^{14–16,18,20–27}. Those spectroscopic investigations have provided important insights into the excited-state dynamics of alkene-based rotary motors, but a definitive explanation of the experimental observations has not yet been achieved. In fact, the numerous experimental studies^{14–16,18,20–27} have been accompanied by only very few computational investigations on the most spectroscopically characterized motors^{28–31}, while most of the reported theoretical studies focused either on alkene rotary motors for which fewer spectroscopic data are available^{32–42} or on computationally designed compounds^{43–50}.

In this work, we investigate a Feringa's first-generation alkene rotary motor with push-pull substituents (compound **1** in Figure 1a), which was recently synthesized and characterized by time-resolved spectroscopy^{16,27}. On the basis of the spectroscopic findings, it was proposed that upon photoexcitation the motor is promoted to a bright excited state that rapidly relaxes to a weak-emissive state, named the dark state, which finally decays back to the ground state, on the picosecond timescale^{16,26,27}. Moreover, in the reported spectroscopic investigations it was shown that the photoinduced dynamics of **1** is significantly affected by the solvent polarity. Specifically, in polar solvents the photorelaxation to the ground state of **1** is accelerated and its quantum yield for the forward photoisomerization (step 1 in Figure 1b) is largely reduced, than in nonpolar solvents^{16,27}. However, to date, a detailed explanation of the reported solvent polarity effects on the light-induced dynamics of **1** is still missing. Understanding such effects is important because changing the medium polarity represents a possible way of fine-tuning the photochemical behaviour of light-driven rotary motors^{15,16,51}.

Herein, we present a computational characterization of the photochemical behaviour of motor **1** in two different solvents: nonpolar cyclohexane and polar methanol. Specifically, we carried out quantum chemical calculations of the low-lying electronic potential energy surfaces (PESs) of **1** using the recently developed mixed-

reference spin-flip time-dependent DFT (MRSF-TDDFT) method^{52,53}, backed by ab initio multireference calculations. Next, we simulated the nonadiabatic excited-state dynamics of **1** in solution using a semiempirical quantum mechanics/molecular mechanics (QM/MM) technique (Figure 1a), and the trajectory surface hopping method^{54,55}. This computational strategy allowed us to achieve a detailed understanding of the photochemical behaviour of **1** and to explain how solvent polarity affects the photoinduced dynamics of our investigated motor.

2 Methods

2.1 Quantum chemical calculations

The ground-state (S_0) minimum-energy geometry of the cis-stable isomer of our investigated push-pull motor (**1c**) was optimized at the DFT level, using the B3LYP functional^{56,57} and the cc-pVDZ basis set⁵⁸. Hessian was computed to check if the S_0 -optimized geometry was an energy minimum. The DFT calculations were performed using the Gaussian 16 software package (Revision C.01)⁵⁹.

The vertical excitation energies and transition dipoles for the S_1 and S_2 states of **1c** were computed at the B3LYP-optimized S_0 geometry with the mixed-reference spin-flip time-dependent DFT (MRSF-TDDFT) method^{52,53}, using the CAM-B3LYP functional⁶⁰. MRSF-TDDFT adopts one-electron spin-flip (SF) excitations from a mixed triplet reference to solve the spin contamination problem of single reference SF-TDDFT, thus allowing the unambiguous identification of the response states as proper singlets or triplets⁵². At variance with linear-response TDDFT, MRSF-TDDFT was shown to predict the correct topology of conical intersections with the ground state and to describe excited states with significant double excitation character^{61,62}. Solvent effects were included in the MRSF-TDDFT simulations of the vertical excitation by means of the Polarizable Continuum Model (PCM), using the integral equation formalism scheme (IEF-PCM)^{63,64} with iterative solver^{65,66}.

To benchmark the MRSF-TDDFT method for our investigated motor, the vertical excitation energies of S_1 and S_2 at the **1c** minimum were also computed using the quasi-degenerate n-electron valence second-order perturbation theory (QD-NEVPT2). In addition, the accuracy of MRSF-TDDFT was assessed at geometries

far from the S_0 minimum by performing QD-NEVPT2 calculations at the S_1 minima and minimum-energy conical intersections between the S_1 and S_0 states of **1**, optimized at the MRSF-TDDFT level (see below). These calculations are presented in Section S1 in the Supplementary Material.

Although the BHHLYP functional was employed in previous works on different molecular rotary motors^{36,40}, in our MRSF-TDDFT calculations we used the CAM-B3LYP functional mainly because of the knowledge acquired from a previous study by one of us on a prototypical first-generation motor³¹. In that work, we found that CAM-B3LYP provides similar results to BHHLYP, but the S_1 vertical excitation energies computed at the MRSF-TDDFT/CAM-B3LYP level are more accurate (i.e. closer to the QD-NEVPT2 energies) than those obtained using BHHLYP, which is confirmed for the push-pull motor investigated in this work (Table S2).

Minimum-energy geometries for the S_1 state and conical intersections (CoIn) between the S_1 and S_0 states were optimized at the MRSF-TDDFT/CAM-B3LYP level. The CoIn optimizations were performed using an algorithm based on a sequential penalty constrained optimization that does not require the calculation of nonadiabatic couplings⁶⁷.

To investigate the main photorelaxation pathways of motor **1**, potential energy profiles for the S_0 , S_1 and S_2 states were computed with the MRSF-TDDFT/CAM-B3LYP method along minimum-energy paths (MEP) and pathways obtained by geodesic interpolations⁶⁸ between selected optimized geometries. For the MEP calculations, we employed the nudged elastic band (NEB) method⁶⁹, an algorithm for finding transition states which does not require Hessian calculations.

All MRSF-TDDFT calculations were carried out using the cc-pVDZ basis set⁵⁸ and the GAMESS program package (July 31, 2022 R1 Public Release Version)⁷⁰. For CoIn optimizations, the GAMESS package was interfaced with the CIOpt program⁶⁷. To perform the MEP calculations with the MRSF-TDDFT method and the NEB algorithm, we interfaced the GAMESS package with the Empathes code⁷¹.

2.2 Nonadiabatic excited-state dynamics simulations

In the nonadiabatic excited-state dynamics simulations, the electronic states of motor **1** were computed using the semiempirical method FOMO-CI (floating occupation molecular orbitals-configuration interaction)^{55,72,73}. The semiempirical FOMO-CI method is a cost-effective technique suited to simulate the photodynamics in large- and medium-size molecular systems^{31,74–83}. Herein, the FOMO-CI calculations were performed using the AM1 form of the semiempirical Hamiltonian⁸⁴, with the AM1 parameters optimized for the unsubstituted motor **1'** in a previous work by one of us³¹ (see Section S4 for more details). Additionally, in the FOMO-CI calculations we employed an active space of 4 electrons in 7 molecular orbitals of π type, a Gaussian energy width for floating occupation of 0.10 Hartree, and a determinant space including all possible excitations within the orbital active space.

As shown in Section S4, our employed semiempirical method, from now on referred to as R-AM1/FOMO-CASCI(4,7), is able to satisfactorily reproduce the relative energies of the S_0 - S_2 states, the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ transition dipole, and selected geometrical coordinates of **1** for (i) the **1c** ground-state minimum, (ii) the S_1 minima, and (iii) the optimized S_1/S_0 CoIn geometries, computed with the DFT/B3LYP and MRSF-TDDFT/CAM-B3LYP methods (Table S5). Our cost-effective semiempirical R-AM1/FOMO-CASCI(4,7) method allowed us to reach simulation times of several picoseconds (see below).

The nonadiabatic excited-state dynamics of **1** was simulated, using a surface hopping (SH) technique, in two different solvents: cyclohexane and methanol. In both cases, the interaction with the solvent was taken into account using a quantum mechanics/molecular mechanics (QM/MM) approach with electrostatic embedding. In particular, one molecule of our investigated motor was placed in a spherical cluster of solvent molecules (Figure 1a), which were all treated at the MM level using the OPLS-AA force field⁸⁵. The spherical cluster for the QM/MM simulations was prepared as described in Section S5 of the Supplementary Material.

The starting conditions (i.e. nuclear coordinates and velocities, and the initial electronic state) for the SH simulations were sampled from QM/MM ground-state thermal trajectories at 300 K that were propagated in time using the Bussi-Parrinello stochastic thermostat⁸⁶. For each solvent, we sampled five QM/MM thermal equi-

librations, each propagated for 10 ps. More details about the ground-state equilibrations are provided in the Supplementary Material (Section S5). In the sampling procedure, the initial electronic state was selected according to the radiative transition probability from the ground state⁷³, within an excitation energy range of 3.47 ± 0.15 eV for the simulations in cyclohexane, and 3.43 ± 0.15 eV in methanol. For both solvents, the selected energy window includes most of the main band of the UV/visible absorption spectrum computed along the thermal equilibrations (Figure S12 in the Supplementary Material).

In the SH simulations, the time evolution of the electronic wavefunction was computed by making use of a locally diabatic representation⁵⁵, and with a time step of 0.5 fs, employed in the integration of both the nuclear and electronic degrees of freedom. This time step was selected on the basis of preliminary SH simulations in gas phase, where we found that the population dynamics obtained using two different time steps, namely 0.2 fs and 0.5 fs, is essentially the same (Figure S11). Therefore, we used a time step of 0.5 fs in the QM/MM simulations, which allowed us to reduce the computational cost. Quantum decoherence effects along the SH trajectories were taken into account using the overlap decoherence correction (ODC) scheme, with the following parameters: $\sigma = 1.0$ a.u. (Gaussian width) and $S_{min} = 5 \times 10^{-3}$ (minimum overlap)^{87,88}. The rescaling of the nuclear velocities after a hop was performed in the direction of the nonadiabatic coupling vector for backward hops (lower to upper state), while the direction of the nuclear momentum was used for forward hops (upper to lower state).

For both investigated solvents, more than 100 SH trajectories were computed, all of which starting from the S_1 state: 106 trajectories for the simulations of **1c** in cyclohexane, and 105 in methanol. Each SH trajectory was propagated for a maximum time of 20 ps, with energy-conserving conditions. Specifically, a threshold (δE) of 8×10^{-3} hartree was used to monitor the conservation of the total QM/MM energy along each SH trajectory and a reduction of the time step (by a factor of 5) was employed in case the total energy was found to differ by more than $\pm \delta E$ from its initial value. The three lowest singlet states (S_0 - S_2) were included in the nonadiabatic SH dynamics and, for each simulation time, the population of each electronic state i was computed as the fraction of SH trajectories running on the i -th PES. Along the SH trajectories, time-resolved fluorescence emission was simulated as described

in Section S7 in the Supplementary Material.

All the dynamics simulations were performed using the MOPAC-PI program⁸⁹, a development version of the MOPAC code in which the QM/MM semiempirical FOMO-CI technique and the SH method were implemented. For the QM/MM calculations, MOPAC-PI was interfaced with the TINKER 8.5 molecular mechanics package⁹⁰.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Ground-state structure and vertical excitation

As a first step of our computational study, we optimized at the DFT/B3LYP level the ground-state geometry for the cis-stable isomer (**1c**) of our investigated push-pull motor. The most important geometrical parameters of the optimized **1c** structure are reported in Figure 2 and Table S3. For comparison, in Figure 2 we also provide the corresponding geometrical parameters for the cis-stable isomer of the unsubstituted motor **1'** (CN and OMe groups replaced with H in Figure 1), computed at the same of theory in a previous work by one of us³¹.

Figure 2: Molecular structures of the minimum-energy cis-stable isomers of motors **1** (push-pull) and **1'** (unsubstituted), computed at the DFT/B3LYP level, with selected geometrical parameters (defined in Figure 1a). For each isomer, only the carbon atoms are shown and two different views are provided. The optimized structure of **1'c** was taken from Ref.³¹.

For **1c**, the equilibrium length of the central C=C bond (r) is 1.365 \AA , while it is 1.363 \AA for **1'c**, indicating that the push-pull substitution leads to a small elongation

of r of 0.002 Å. The dihedral angle θ , which quantifies the twisting around the central C=C axle, is about the same in **1c** and **1'c**, i.e. $\sim 4^\circ$, and deviates from the planar value of 0° . This partial twisting can be attributed to the steric repulsion between the two halves of the motor, which is essentially unaltered by the push-pull substitution.

Among the different geometrical parameters of motors **1** and **1'**, in Figure 2 we also report the pyramidalizations of the carbon atoms connected by the central C=C bond, which are quantified with the two dihedrals φ and φ' (defined in Figure 1a). As it can be observed, in both **1c** and **1'c**, φ and φ' only slightly deviate from 0° (no pyramidalization). However, while in **1'c** φ and φ' assume exactly the same value, in **1c** the push-pull substitution causes a symmetry breaking of the molecular geometry, as indicated by the small deviation between φ and φ' (Figure 2).

By further analyzing the optimized ground-state structures, it is possible to notice that in both **1c** and **1'c** the conformation of the cyclopentadiene rings in the two halves of the motor is such that the two methyl groups of the stereocenters are in the axial positions. This can be quantified by the β and β' dihedrals, which are positive in both **1c** and **1'c** (Figure 2). Similarly to what was shown for the unsubstituted motor **1'** in our previous work³¹, in the push-pull motor **1** the cis-trans photoisomerization of the central C=C bond is accompanied by a conformational inversion in both halves of the motor, as indicated by the change of β and β' from positive to negative values in going from **1c** to **1tm** (Table S7).

For the **1c** ground-state isomer, we computed the vertical excitation energies of the two lowest singlet excited states, S_1 and S_2 , using the MRSF-TDDFT method. These calculations were performed in gas-phase and in two different solvents, namely cyclohexane (CyH) and methanol (MeOH), in the latter cases using the PCM model (see Section 2.1, for more details). The obtained excitation energies are reported in Table 1, in which we also provide the corresponding transition dipoles and oscillator strengths from the ground state, as well as the most important electronic configurations in the S_1 and S_2 states.

Table 1: Vertical excitation energies (eV), transition dipoles (modulus in Debye, D) and oscillator strengths from the ground state (S_0), and main electronic configurations for the S_1 and S_2 states of **1c** in gas phase, cyclohexane (CyH) and methanol (MeOH), computed with the MRSF-TDDFT/CAM-B3LYP method at the DFT/B3LYP optimized geometries. Only the electronic configurations with a weight larger than 0.10 are reported. In the definition of the electronic configurations, we used H to indicate HOMO and L to indicate LUMO.

Medium	State	Energy	Trans. Dipole	Osci. Strength	Configuration	Weight
Gas phase	S_1	3.37	8.418	0.905	$H \rightarrow L$	0.819
					$H - 1 \rightarrow L$	0.126
	S_2	3.99	3.403	0.176	$H - 1 \rightarrow L$	0.523
CyH	S_1	3.28	8.332	0.865	$H \rightarrow L$	0.822
					$H - 1 \rightarrow L$	0.125
	S_2	3.98	3.856	0.224	$H - 1 \rightarrow L$	0.543
MeOH	S_1	3.11	8.233	0.799	$H \rightarrow L$	0.835
					$H - 1 \rightarrow L$	0.113
	S_2	3.94	4.494	0.302	$H - 1 \rightarrow L$	0.568
					$H \rightarrow L + 1$	0.220

In all the investigated media, the lowest singlet excited state (S_1) of **1c** is associated with a large transition dipole from S_0 and therefore is optically bright. The $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ vertical transition mainly corresponds to a single-electron excitation from the HOMO π -bonding to the LUMO π -antibonding orbital of the central C=C bond (Figure S2), but also shows a smaller contribution from the HOMO-1 \rightarrow LUMO single-electron transition. The second lowest singlet excited state (S_2) of **1c** features a smaller transition dipole from S_0 , compared to S_1 , and is dominated by the HOMO-1 \rightarrow LUMO one-electron excitation, with an additional large contribution from the HOMO \rightarrow LUMO+1 singly-excited configuration. By comparing these results with those obtained for the unsubstituted motor³¹ (Table S4), one can see that the push-pull substitution leads to an increase of the HOMO-1 \rightarrow LUMO contribution in both S_1 and S_2 , the latter state becoming dominated by HOMO-1 \rightarrow LUMO in **1c**. As one can observe from Figure S2, the HOMO-1 \rightarrow LUMO transition has a significant charge-transfer character in **1c**, with electron density

flowing from the lower OMe-substituted half to the upper CN-substituted half.

For **1c** in gas-phase, the MRSF-TDDFT vertical excitation energy of S_1 is 3.37 eV, a value which is close to the energy computed at the QD-NEVPT2 level (3.26 eV, Table S1). Both the MRSF-TDDFT and QD-NEVPT2 predict that the S_1 vertical excitation energy is red-shifted by about 0.3 eV in **1c**, compared to **1'c** (Table S4). This result agrees well with the spectroscopic evidence that the maximum of the UV/vis absorption spectrum of **1c** is red-shifted from **1'c** by ~ 0.3 eV in cyclohexane and ~ 0.4 eV in methanol¹⁶.

For **1c** in solution, our MRSF-TDDFT/PCM calculations predict a red-shift of the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ transition energy of 0.09 eV in nonpolar cyclohexane and 0.26 eV in polar methanol, compared to gas-phase (Table 1). Therefore, for **1c** the computed red-shift from cyclohexane to methanol is 0.17 eV, which is in good agreement the spectroscopic red-shift of ca. 0.1 eV^{16,27}.

Both the MRSF-TDDFT and QD-NEVPT2 results indicate that, at the **1c** S_0 minimum, the S_2 state is energetically well separated from S_1 : in gas-phase, the S_2 - S_1 energy gap is larger than 0.6 eV at both the MRSF-TDDFT and QD-NEVPT2 levels, respectively (Tables 1 and S1). According to our MRSF-TDDFT/PCM calculations, the S_2 - S_1 energy gap becomes even larger (≥ 0.7 eV) in both cyclohexane and methanol, due to the larger solvent stabilization of S_1 compared to S_2 (Table 1).

3.2 Photorelaxation potential energy profiles in gas-phase

To investigate the possible relaxation pathways upon photoexcitation of **1c**, we searched for the local minima in the lowest bright S_1 state, using the MRSF-TDDFT/CAM-B3LYP method. We found two different S_1 minima, S_1 -min₁₋₂, with θ values of 24° and 80°, and S_1 energies of 3.03 eV and 2.51 eV, relative to the **1c** S_0 minimum, respectively (Figure 3a and Table S7).

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Figure 3: **a** Molecular structures of the S_1 minima $S_1\text{-min}_1$ and $S_1\text{-min}_2$, and the minimum-energy S_1/S_0 conical intersection CoIn_1 of motor **1**, with selected geometrical parameters (defined in Figure 1a). For each structure, only the carbon atoms are shown and two different views are provided. **b** Potential energy paths between selected optimized geometries for motor **1**, computed using the MRSF-TDDFT/CAM-B3LYP method. The paths $\mathbf{1c} \rightarrow S_1\text{-min}_1$ and $S_1\text{-min}_2 \rightarrow \text{CoIn}_1$ were obtained by geodesic interpolation, while the $S_1\text{-min}_1 \rightarrow S_1\text{-min}_2$ pathway is a minimum-energy path on the S_1 state. The potential energies (eV) of the S_0 , S_1 and S_2 states, as well as the $S_1\text{-}S_0$ energy gap, are shown. **c** Selected geometrical parameters of **1** along the paths. **d** Transition dipoles (modulus in Debye) from S_0 to the S_1 and S_2 states. **e** Partial charge (a.u.) of the OMe-substituted lower half of **1** in the S_0 , S_1 and S_2 states.

Next, we computed the potential energy profiles of the three lowest singlet states

(S_0 - S_2) along the following paths: (i) $\mathbf{1c} \rightarrow S_{1\text{-min}_1}$, and (ii) $S_{1\text{-min}_1} \rightarrow S_{1\text{-min}_2}$, the former obtained by geodesic interpolation⁶⁸, while the latter by minimum-energy path calculation (see Section 2.1 for more details). The obtained potential energy curves are presented in Figure 3, in which we also show selected geometrical parameters of $\mathbf{1}$, the transition dipoles of the S_1 and S_2 states, and the partial charge of the OMe-substituted lower half of the motor in the S_0 - S_2 states. The reported partial charge was determined by summing the Mulliken atomic charges of the lower half of $\mathbf{1}$, computed using the S_0 - S_2 electron densities.

As it can be observed from Figure 3b, a downhill pathway in the S_1 state connects the $\mathbf{1c}$ Franck-Condon (FC) point to $S_{1\text{-min}_1}$. This path mainly involves an elongation of the central C=C bond (r) and a partial twisting around the same bond (θ) of the motor (Figure 3c). Along the same path, the S_1 state is emissive (large $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ transition dipole, Figure 3d) and its energy separation from S_0 is large (> 2.5 eV), as confirmed by QD-NEVPT2 calculations at the $\mathbf{1c}$ and $S_{1\text{-min}_1}$ geometries (Table S1).

The minimum-energy pathway connecting $S_{1\text{-min}_1}$ to $S_{1\text{-min}_2}$ on the S_1 PES is characterized by a small energy barrier of 0.055 eV (5.3 kJ/mol), corresponding to a transition-state geometry with $\theta = 61^\circ$ ($S_{1\text{-ts}_{12}}$), at the MRSF-TDDFT level (Figure 3b). Similarly to the $\mathbf{1c} \rightarrow S_{1\text{-min}_1}$ path, along $S_{1\text{-min}_1} \rightarrow S_{1\text{-min}_2}$ the motor undergoes an increase of r and a further twisting around θ (Figure 3c). Moreover, one can see that two additional geometrical changes are involved along the $S_{1\text{-min}_1} \rightarrow S_{1\text{-min}_2}$ pathway: (i) the conformational inversion of both halves of the motor, with β and β' changing from positive to negative values, and (ii) the partial pyramidalization on one half, as indicated by the increase of φ' (Figure 3c). Along $S_{1\text{-min}_1} \rightarrow S_{1\text{-min}_2}$, the energy barrier crossing leads to a PES region, around $S_{1\text{-min}_2}$, in which the S_1 is essentially dark (i.e. nonfluorescent, $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ transition dipole modulus > 2 Debye, Figure 3d) and the S_1 - S_0 energy gap is quite small (> 1 eV).

As one can observe from Figure 3e, along the $\mathbf{1c} \rightarrow S_{1\text{-min}_1}$ path both halves of the motor exhibit a very small partial charge for all the S_0 , S_1 and S_2 states. On the other hand, in the $S_{1\text{-min}_1} \rightarrow S_{1\text{-min}_2}$ pathway the motor undergoes a large charge-polarization in the S_1 state, with a partial negative charge moving from the lower

OMe-substituted half (which acquires a positive charge) to the upper CN-substituted half. Along the same $S_1\text{-min}_1 \rightarrow S_1\text{-min}_2$ path a moderate charge separation between the two halves occurs in the S_2 state (in the opposite direction, compared to S_1) and essentially no polarization is observed in the S_0 state (Figure 3e).

The potential energy profiles for **1** are qualitatively similar to those obtained for the unsubstituted motor **1'** in our previous work³¹. However, as shown in Figure S3, the push-pull substitution introduces two important effects, which are: (i) a significant lowering of the energy barrier along the pathway from $S_1\text{-min}_1$ to $S_1\text{-min}_2$ on the S_1 PES in going from **1'** to **1**, and (ii) a large reduction of the $S_1\text{-}S_0$ energy gap at the twisted minimum $S_1\text{-min}_2$, from 1.22 eV for **1'** to 0.55 eV for **1**, at the MRSF-TDDFT level.

From Figure 3b, one can observe that, although for motor **1** the $S_1\text{-}S_0$ energy gap significantly decreases along the $S_1\text{-min}_1 \rightarrow S_1\text{-min}_2$ paths, even at largely twisted geometries around $S_1\text{-min}_2$ the S_1 and S_0 states are quite far from being degenerate. Specifically, at the $S_1\text{-min}_2$ geometry the $S_1\text{-}S_0$ energy difference is 0.55 eV at the MRSF-TDDFT level and 0.67 eV using the QD-NEVPT2 method (Table S1). To study the possible role of CoIns in the excited-state decay of motor **1**, we searched for the minimum-energy CoIns between the S_1 and S_0 states using the MRSF-TDDFT method, starting from the twisted geometry of $S_1\text{-min}_2$. We identified one S_1/S_0 CoIn (CoIn₁) closely related to the $S_1\text{-min}_2$ geometry. In particular, as shown in Figure 3a, CoIn₁ features a significant twisting around the C=C axle ($\theta = 66^\circ$), a large pyramidalization at only one of the carbon atoms of the central C=C bond, namely C_{1'} (with φ and φ' respectively equal to -2° and 21°), and a strong charge-polarization in the S_1 state (Figure 3e).

Taking as reference the **1c** S_0 minimum, the energy of CoIn₁ is 3.03 eV at the MRSF-TDDFT level. Therefore, despite the $S_1\text{-min}_2 \rightarrow \text{CoIn}_1$ path is essentially barrierless (Figure 3b), CoIn₁ lies energetically above the largely twisted minimum $S_1\text{-min}_2$ (located at 2.51 eV, Table S7), with an energy difference between CoIn₁ and $S_1\text{-min}_2$ of 0.52 eV. From Figure 3b, one can observe that CoIn₁ is located below the S_1 energy at **1c** S_0 minima and is isoenergetic with $S_1\text{-min}_1$ (see also Table S7) and therefore, starting from those two geometries on the S_1 PES, the motor might have enough energy to reach CoIn₁. However, interpolated paths between CoIn₁ and

both the **1c** and S_1 -min₁ geometries indicate the presence of high energy barriers in the S_1 state (Figure S10). These results suggest that, after excitation to the lowest bright S_1 state, CoIn₁ is not easily accessible.

3.3 Nonadiabatic excited-state dynamics in solution

To study the photorelaxation dynamics of motor **1** after excitation of the **1c** isomer, we performed QM/MM nonadiabatic excited-state dynamics simulations in two different solvents, namely cyclohexane (nonpolar) and methanol (polar). For these simulations, we used the trajectory surface hopping (SH) method and a reparametrized semiempirical electronic structure technique, as described in Section 2.2.

For both solvents, the whole set of SH trajectories started from S_1 , which is the lowest bright state at the **1c** S_0 minimum (Table 1). Figure 4 shows the population dynamics for the S_0 , S_1 and S_2 states of motor **1**, as obtained from the SH simulations with excitation of **1c** in cyclohexane and methanol. As it can be observed, in both solvents the main relaxation mechanism is the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ internal conversion, which is completed in a few picoseconds after the photoexcitation. The upper-lying S_2 state was also included in our SH simulations, but its population is close to zero throughout the dynamics.

Figure 4: Populations of the S_0 , S_1 and S_2 states for **1c** in cyclohexane (panel **a**) and in methanol (panel **b**), as obtained in the surface hopping simulations. In each panel, the single-exponential fitting function for the S_1 population is also shown (dashed black line).

The decay of the S_1 population is well fit by a delayed single-exponential function

(Eq. S1 in Section S6) in both cyclohexane and methanol (Figure 4, dashed black line). The extracted time constants (τ_1) are 4.6 ps in cyclohexane and 2.4 ps in methanol, while the corresponding delay times (t_0) are 1.1 ps and 0.3 ps, respectively (Table 2). Therefore, the extracted S_1 lifetimes ($\tau_1 + t_0$) are 5.7 ps in cyclohexane and 2.7 ps in methanol. Thus, our simulations predict that, after excitation of **1c**, the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ conversion is about two times faster in methanol, compared to cyclohexane.

In the early spectroscopic investigation of motor **1**, the time evolution of the transient absorption spectrum of **1c** was fit to a sequential two-step model and the reported lifetime of the intermediate excited-state species, which decays to the final ground state, is 4.5 ps in cyclohexane and 1.6 ps in methanol¹⁶. Therefore, the time constants of excited-state decay (τ_1) extracted from our simulations, namely 4.6 ps in cyclohexane and 2.4 ps in methanol, are in good agreement with the reported spectroscopic lifetimes (Table 2). Moreover, the shortening of the excited-state lifetime of **1c** in going from cyclohexane to methanol is well reproduced by our calculations.

Table 2: Delay time (t_0), time constant of excited-state decay (τ_1), and S_1 state lifetime (τ_{S1}) for **1c** in cyclohexane (CyH) and methanol (MeOH), as obtained from the surface hopping simulations. t_0 and τ_1 were determined by fitting the S_1 population with a delayed single-exponential function, and τ_{S1} is the sum of t_0 and τ_1 . The experimental time comparable to τ_1 , obtained by time-resolved spectroscopic¹⁶, is also reported.

Solvent	t_0	τ_1	τ_{S1}	Exp. ¹⁶ (τ_1)
CyH	1.1 ps	4.6 ps	5.7 ps	4.5 ps
MeOH	0.3 ps	2.4 ps	2.7 ps	1.6 ps

To achieve a more detailed comparison of our simulations with the spectroscopic investigations^{16,27}, we computed along the SH trajectories the time-resolved fluorescence emission reported in Figure 5a-b. A detailed description of how we determined the fluorescence emission intensity in our simulations is provided in Section S7. As it can be observed from Figure 5a-b, the time-resolved emission features an initial ultrafast decay, which is followed by a weaker, longer-lived emission. In both solvents, the fluorescence emission decay is well fit by a triple-exponential function (Eq. S2, dashed black line in Figure 5a-b) with a very fast decay time (τ_{f1}), that we set equal to 5 fs and kept constant in our fitting procedure, and two slower relaxation

times (τ_{f2} and τ_{f3} , obtained from the fitting) respectively equal to 1.0 ps and 3.0 ps in cyclohexane, and 0.2 ps and 2.2 ps in methanol (Table 3). Therefore, τ_{f2} and τ_{f3} are significantly shorter in methanol, compared to cyclohexane, indicating a faster decay of the two longer-lived emission components in the polar solvent.

Figure 5: Time-evolution of the fluorescence emission intensity (ns^{-1}) and of the C=C torsional dihedral (θ , in degree), averaged over all trajectories running on the S_1 state, for **1c** in cyclohexane (panels **a**, **c**) and in methanol (panels **b**, **d**), as obtained in the surface hopping simulations. In panels **a-b**, the inset shows the time-resolved fluorescence emission in the first 150 fs of the simulations.

Time-resolved fluorescence measurements for motor **1** are reported in Refs.^{16,27}. In those studies, the fluorescence decay was fitted using a sum of three exponentials, including an ultrafast component and two slower decay constants of 0.37 ps and 3.2 ps in cyclohexane, and 0.44 ps and 1.8 ps in methanol²⁷. Thus, both the spectroscopic slower decay times are of the same order of magnitude as those obtained in our simulations (τ_{f2} and τ_{f3} , Table 3). Moreover, the time constants of the longer-lived emission component extracted from our calculations, namely 3.0 ps in cyclohexane and 2.2 ps in methanol (τ_{f3} , Table 3), are very close to the corresponding spectro-

scopic values of 3.2 ps and 1.8 ps, respectively²⁷.

Table 3: Time constants of fluorescence decay (τ_{f1} , τ_{f2} and τ_{f3}) for **1c** in cyclohexane (CyH) and methanol (MeOH), as obtained from the surface hopping simulations. τ_{f1} , τ_{f2} and τ_{f3} were determined from the fit of the time-resolved integrated fluorescence decay using a triple-exponential function, and their relative weights (in parentheses) and weighted average (τ_f^{avg}) are also reported. The experimental times comparable to τ_{f2} and τ_{f3} , obtained by time-resolved fluorescence measurements²⁷, are also reported.

Solvent	τ_{f1}	τ_{f2}	τ_{f3}	τ_f^{avg}	Exp. ²⁷ (τ_{f2} , τ_{f3})
CyH	5.0 fs (31%)	1.0 ps (40%)	3.0 ps (29%)	1.3 ps	0.37 ps, 3.2 ps
MeOH	5.0 fs (28%)	0.2 ps (24%)	2.2 ps (48%)	1.1 ps	0.44 ps, 1.8 ps

In order to connect the fluorescence decay with the geometrical changes of **1** after the photoexcitation, in Figure 5 (panels c-d) we also show the time evolution of the C=C torsional dihedral θ , averaged over all trajectories running on the S_1 state. As it can be observed, in the first ~ 1 -2 ps of the simulations the motor undergoes a large torsion around θ towards more twisted geometries, compared to the initial **1c** structure (Time = 0). In both solvents, this large variation of θ essentially occurs in the same time interval of the initial fast decay of the fluorescence emission, indicating that this initial emission decay is mainly driven by a torsion around θ . At longer times (> 2 ps), the averaged value of θ starts oscillating around a nearly constant value of about 65° in cyclohexane and 40° in methanol (Figure 5c-d). This suggests that the longer-lived fluorescence arises from emission at twisted excited-state geometries. We anticipate that these twisted geometries mainly correspond to the excited-state minima S_1 -min₁ and S_1 -min₂ (Figure 3a), which are associated with a reduced S_1 - S_0 energy gap (compared to the S_0 **1c** minimum), but a non-zero $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ transition dipole (Figure 3b,d), thereby featuring a non-negligible emission intensity (Eq. S3).

To analyse in more detail the molecular geometries of motor **1** visited during the SH simulations, in Figure 6 we report the distributions of θ and the S_1 - S_0 energy gap at different times: at the starting time (Time = 0), when the SH trajectories are running on S_1 (S_1 active), and at the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ hopping geometries. For S_1 active, the two-dimensional distribution of θ as a function of time is also shown (Figure 6c-d). In both solvents, the distribution of θ for the starting geometries (Time = 0) is

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centered at values corresponding to the **1c** minimum-energy ground-state structure (Figures 6a-b and 2). After the photoexcitation, the motor starts visiting the S_1 PES and undergoes a large twisting along θ (Figures 6a-d and S13).

Figure 6: Distributions of the C=C torsional dihedral (θ , in degree) and the S_1 - S_0 energy gap (in eV) for the starting geometries (Time = 0), those visited in the S_1 state (S_1 active), and the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ hopping geometries, as obtained in the surface hopping simulations for **1c** in cyclohexane (panels **a**, **e**) and in methanol (panels **b**, **f**). The two-dimensional distribution of θ in the S_1 state (S_1 active) as a function of time is also shown (panels **c-d**). In panels **a-d**, the θ values of the S_1 minima (min_{1-2} , dashed grey lines), computed at the semiempirical R-AM1/FOMO-CASCI(4,7) level in gas phase, are reported. In panels **a-b**, the sub-distributions of $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ hopping geometries corresponding to reactive and unreactive trajectories (black and green colors, respectively) are also shown.

In cyclohexane, the distribution of θ for S_1 active is characterized by two separate peaks (Figure 6a,c), one centered at around 35° , corresponding to the S_1 -min₁ structure, and a second band with maximum at around 85° , which can be associated with the S_1 -min₂ geometry (Figure 3). The θ distribution for S_1 active in methanol is significantly different: one can observe the presence of only one intense peak centered at around 30° , which can be related to S_1 -min₁, and a much lower band for θ values between 60° and 90° (Figure 6b,d).

The presence of two distinct peaks in the θ distribution for S_1 active suggests that during the photorelaxation dynamics the excited-state trajectories are split between two different S_1 PES regions, which essentially correspond to the S_1 -min₁ and S_1 -min₂ geometries of **1**. As shown in Figure S13, the population split occurs after the first crossing of the barrier between the two S_1 minima ($\theta \sim 60^\circ$), taking place in about 0.9 ps in cyclohexane and 0.3 ps in methanol after the photoexcitation. These times roughly match both the delay time of the S_1 population decay (t_0 , Table 2) and the second time constant of fluorescence decay (τ_{f2} , Table 3). The fact that in methanol the first barrier crossing takes place at shorter times than in cyclohexane can be ascribed to a lowering of the energy barrier between S_1 -min₁ and S_1 -min₂ in polar methanol. As observed in Figure 3e, along the S_1 -min₁ \rightarrow S_1 -min₂ path the charge-polarization in the S_1 state develops before the barrier crossing. Therefore, the energy barrier lowering in methanol can be attributed by a stabilization of the polarized S_1 state by solvent polarity.

In both solvents, the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ conversion occurs at largely twisted geometries ($\theta > 50^\circ$, Figure 6a-b). While in cyclohexane the θ distribution for the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ hops peaks at around 90° , a value that essentially corresponds to the gas-phase S_1 -min₂ structure, in methanol most of the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ transitions take place at less twisted geometries (distribution maximum at $\theta \simeq 80^\circ$). Additionally, in both solvents the hopping geometries are associated with much smaller S_1 - S_0 energy gaps (< 1.5 eV) and largely reduced $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ transition dipoles, compared to the starting geometries (Figures 6e-f and S16a-b). However, while in cyclohexane most of the SH trajectories decay to S_0 with S_1 - S_0 energy gap of about 1.0 eV (Figure 6e), a value which matches the gap for S_1 -min₂ computed at the semiempirical R-AM1/FOMO-CASCI(4,7) level in gas-phase (Table S5), in methanol the distribution of S_1 - S_0 energy gaps at the hopping geometries is shifted towards significantly smaller values and peaks at ~ 0.2

eV (Figure 6f).

By looking at Figure 6a-d, one may have the wrong impression that the barrier to reach S_1 -min₂ is higher in methanol, than in cyclohexane, as for methanol the θ probability distribution in the S_1 state (S_1 active) is significantly lower at twisted geometries. However, the lower θ distribution in S_1 at larger θ values (close to S_1 -min₂) is mainly due to the fact that in methanol the largely twisted geometries are visited for a shorter time interval, than in cyclohexane, due to the fast $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ conversion, which in turn is caused by the very small S_1 - S_0 energy gap at twisted geometries (Figure 6b,f).

Along the SH trajectories we also analysed the pyramidalization coordinates, namely φ and φ' , and the β and β' dihedrals, which are indicative of the conformation of the two halves of **1**. As shown in Figure S16c-f, in both the investigated solvents, motor **1** undergoes small variations along φ and φ' in going from the starting time to the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ hopping geometries, featuring much smaller pyramidalization values than those required to reach CoIn₁ (Figure 3a), which is never accessed in our simulations. On the other hand, larger variations occur along β and β' (Figure S16g-j). In particular, β and β' are positive at the starting geometries, but their distributions are shifted towards smaller values at the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ hopping geometries. This shift is more pronounced in cyclohexane, than in methanol (Figure 16g-j). Specifically, in cyclohexane most of the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ hops are associated with negative β and β' and therefore with a conformational geometry of the two halves of the motor closer to the **1tm** isomer (Figure 1b and Table S7), rather than **1c**.

To further examine the molecular geometries and S_1 PES regions where the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ transition takes place, we performed QM/MM geometry optimizations for the S_1 state starting from the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ hopping geometries of the SH simulations. As shown in Figure S14, for both cyclohexane and methanol, the distributions of θ and the S_1 - S_0 energy gap for the optimized structures (S_1 min) have their maxima at values very close to those of the corresponding distributions for the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ hopping geometries. Therefore, we identify these hopping structures as those corresponding to a region of the S_1 PES around a largely twisted minimum. While in cyclohexane the twisted excited-state minimum has similar features to the gas-phase S_1 -min₂, in methanol the corresponding S_1 minimum is associated with a less twisted geometry

(i.e. with a smaller value of θ) and a largely reduced S_1 - S_0 energy gap.

In order to investigate the origin of the reduced S_1 - S_0 energy gap at transition geometries in methanol, we computed the charge separation between the two halves of the motor in the S_1 and S_0 states at selected geometries of the SH simulations. In Figure 7, we report the distributions of the partial charge of the OMe-substituted lower half of motor **1** in the S_1 and S_0 states for the starting geometries (Time = 0) and the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ hops.

As it can be observed, in both methanol and cyclohexane, at the starting geometries (Time = 0) the charge polarization of the motor is very small in the S_1 and S_0 states (Figure 7). On the other hand, at the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ hopping geometries the motor exhibits a large charge transfer between its two halves in the S_1 state, with a partial negative charge flowing from OMe-substituted half to the CN-substituted half, in both the investigated solvents. Instead, at the same hopping geometries there is no significant charge polarization in the S_0 state. These results indicate that the large reduction in the S_1 - S_0 energy gap at hopping geometries in polar methanol, compared to cyclohexane, can be mainly attributed to the solvent stabilization of the polarized (charge-transfer) S_1 state, relative to the unpolarized S_0 state, at largely twisted geometries. The development of a “sudden charge-polarization” in the excited state along the photorelaxation path was also observed in the unsubstituted motor **1'** in our previous work³¹ and was reported in earlier studies of cis-trans photoisomerization of ethylenic compounds^{91–94}.

Figure 7: Distributions of the partial charge (in a.u.) of the OMe-substituted lower half of motor **1** in the S_1 and S_0 states for the starting geometries (Time = 0) and the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ hopping geometries, as obtained in the surface hopping simulations in cyclohexane (panel a) and in methanol (panel b).

In order to further examine the solvent effects on the photorelaxation dynamics in methanol, we analysed the possible formation of a hydrogen bond between the CN group of the QM motor and the OH group of one MM methanol molecule. We found that at the starting geometries (Time = 0) and those of the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ hops the hydrogen bond is present in only a moderate fraction of structures, namely 11% at Time = 0 and 24% at the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ hops, using a maximum N–O distance threshold of 3.0 Å for the identification of a hydrogen bond (Table S6). These fractions of hydrogen-bond structures increase to 17% at Time = 0 and 34% at the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ hops if a maximum N–O distance threshold of 3.5 Å is employed (Table S6). However, in both cases, the effect of the hydrogen bond formation on the population dynamics in methanol is very small, as it can be observed from Figure S8, where we compare the populations computed using all the SH trajectories and only the trajectories where no hydrogen bond is present at the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ hopping geometries (i.e. the trajectories with a hydrogen bond are excluded). In addition, the sub-distributions of θ and the S_1 - S_0 energy gap for the starting and the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ hopping geometries where a hydrogen bond is absent or present are very similar (Figure S9). Therefore, this analysis confirms that the faster photorelaxation dynamics in methanol is mainly caused by solvent polarity effects, rather than the hydrogen bond formation, which has a very minor role in the dynamics.

On the basis of the electronic populations dynamics, the fluorescence emission decay and the main photorelaxation geometrical changes obtained in our simulations, the excited-state dynamics of motor **1** in solution can be summarized as follows. After the initial excitation to the S_1 bright state, the motor undergoes an ultrafast initial twisting along θ towards the closest excited-state minimum S_1 -min₁. This is followed by a further twisting around θ to cross the barrier between S_1 -min₁ and the lowest excited-state minimum S_1 -min₂. The barrier crossing occurs at shorter times in methanol, than in cyclohexane, an effect that can be ascribed to an energy barrier lowering due to the stabilization of the charge-polarized S_1 state by solvent polarity. After the first barrier crossing, the excited-state population is split between the two S_1 minima, namely S_1 -min₁ and S_1 -min₂ (Figures 6 and S13). As the S_1 -min₁ PES region is associated with a larger $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ transition dipole, compared to S_1 -min₂, and the S_1 -min₁ sub-population has a lifetime of several picoseconds, we attribute the slower fluorescence decay component (τ_{F3} , Table 3) mainly to the emission from

S_1 -min₁, in both cyclohexane and methanol. After accessing the largely twisted minimum S_1 -min₂, the motor relaxes back to the ground-state. At the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ transition geometries (around S_1 -min₂) the S_1 state has a significant charge-transfer character and is largely stabilized by solvent polarity, relative to the unpolarized S_0 state. This effect leads to a smaller S_1 - S_0 energy gap around S_1 -min₂ and a faster $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ nonradiative decay in polar methanol. Therefore, according to our simulations, the faster excited-state relaxation of motor **1** in methanol, compared to cyclohexane, can be mainly ascribed to the reduced S_1 - S_0 energy gap at transition geometries (around S_1 -min₂) and, to a lesser extent, to a lowering of the energy barrier towards S_1 -min₂ in methanol.

In contrast to what was proposed in the spectroscopic investigations for motor **1**^{16,27}, according to our simulations the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ conversion exclusively takes place from a PES region around a largely twisted S_1 minimum, rather than a CoIn point. While in polar methanol the energy gap at the largely twisted minimum is very small, in cyclohexane the S_1 and S_0 states at the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ transition geometries are quite far from being degenerate (Figure 6e-f).

After the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ conversion, the swarm of SH trajectories is split between the **1c** and **1tm** ground-state minima. To determine the quantum yield of photoisomerization, we divided the SH trajectories into reactive and unreactive: the trajectories visiting the **1tm** ground-state minimum at the end of the simulation (Time = 20 ps) are labeled as reactive, while the other unreactive (Figure S15). The photoisomerization yield is computed as the percentage of reactive trajectories (Φ) and its standard deviation using the binomial formula $\sqrt{\Phi(100 - \Phi)/N_T}$, where N_T is the total number of SH trajectories. The **1c** \rightarrow **1tm** photoisomerization quantum yield obtained in our simulations in cyclohexane is 78.3 ± 4.0 %, while it significantly reduces to 21.9 ± 4.0 % in methanol. The corresponding experimental yields are 99% in cyclohexane and 5% in methanol¹⁶. Therefore, our simulations confirm the experimental finding that the photoisomerization yield of motor **1** undergoes a large reduction in going from nonpolar cyclohexane to polar methanol.

4 Conclusions

In this work, we have studied the photoinduced dynamics of a push-pull alkene-based first-generation rotary motor in two different solvents, namely cyclohexane and methanol. In our investigation, we combined quantum chemical calculations at the MRSF-TDDFT and QD-NEVPT2 levels with surface hopping nonadiabatic dynamics simulations using a semiempirical QM/MM technique. Our aim was to achieve a detailed understanding of the solvent polarity effects on the excited-state dynamics of our investigated molecular motor, as well as to provide a clear explanation of the reported spectroscopic findings.

We showed that, for the most stable ground-state isomer of the motor (**1c**), the lowest optically bright excited state is S_1 , whose excitation energy and nature are only moderately affected by both the push-pull substitution and solvent polarity. Our excited-state geometry optimizations revealed the presence of two S_1 minima, S_1 -min₁ and S_1 -min₂, separated by a low energy barrier. S_1 -min₁ is closer to the **1c** Franck-Condon (FC) point and is optically bright (i.e. emissive), while the largely twisted S_1 -min₂ is essentially dark and features a significant charge-transfer character. Moreover, the main geometrical changes connecting the FC point with S_1 -min₁ and S_1 -min₂ are: (i) the torsion around the central C=C bond (θ), and (ii) the conformational inversion of both halves of the motor.

Our QM/MM nonadiabatic dynamics simulations in solution indicated that, in both cyclohexane and methanol, the main photorelaxation mechanism involves a very fast geometrical relaxation from the FC point to the bright S_1 -min₁, which provides the most important contribution to the fluorescence emission, followed by a barrier crossing to form the dark, largely twisted S_1 -min₂, from which the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ conversion takes place. In agreement with the spectroscopic findings, we found that the photorelaxation dynamics of our investigated motor is significantly faster in polar methanol, compared to nonpolar cyclohexane. We attributed the accelerated dynamics in methanol to two main effects: (i) a lowering of the energy barrier between S_1 -min₁ and S_1 -min₂, and (ii) a reduction of the S_1 - S_0 energy gap at geometries around S_1 -min₂. We showed that both effects can be attributed to solvent-polarity stabilization of the charge-transfer S_1 state along the photorelaxation pathway. Additionally, our dynamics simulations confirm the experimental evidence that the

forward photoisomerization yield of the motor is largely affected by solvent polarity, causing a large yield reduction from cyclohexane to methanol.

Overall, our study reveals the excited-state dynamics of a push-pull Feringa's first-generation rotary motor in solution and provides a detailed interpretation of the spectroscopic observations, thereby contributing to uncovering how solvent polarity can impact the photochemical behaviour of light-driven rotary molecular motors.

Supplementary Material

The supplementary material includes additional information about the QD-NEVPT2 quantum chemical calculations, the comparison of exchange-correlation functionals, the comparison of push-pull and unsubstituted motors, and the semiempirical method for the dynamics simulations. It also encompasses details about the preparation of the QM/MM system, the thermal equilibrations, the fitting functions, the calculation of time-resolved emission, and the hydrogen bond analysis, as well as supplementary tables and figures.

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